

Consumer Legal Forum of Bangladesh: A Comparative Study with India and Pakistan

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Abstract

For the growth of national and international trade, protecting consumers' rights is a significant and vital responsibility of the State. India and Pakistan are aware of their consumers' rights. They have amended or enacted laws and incorporated provisions to save the rights of the consumers. They have also established Corporate Legal Forum under their consumer protection Acts. These forums are highly active. On the other hand, Bangladesh is slightly behind in this regard. It has only one statute, Consumer Protection Act (CPA)2009. However, Bangladesh has never amended this law to fight against new trends of infringement of consumers' rights. In comparison, India and Pakistan have modified their laws regularly. Under CPA 2009, Courts are empowered in Bangladesh to give aggrieved consumers remedies. However, they are not active for various reasons, and it seems very tough to protect consumers' rights without any dedicated Corporate Legal Forum. There is no corporate legal forum that deals with consumer disputes. Also, there is no safeguard for digital marketing and e-commerce. Agencies and authorities lack human resources. To establish consumer rights in Bangladesh, the government must eradicate these hindrances. This article finds some loopholes in recent forums and suggests the best forum to establish consumer rights in Bangladesh by discussing the corporate legal forum of India and Pakistan.

Keywords: Consumer Rights, Consumer Protection, Legal Forum

Introduction

With the expansion of business types, disputes between the parties increased. Corporate disputes do not entirely fall within the civil wrong or criminal offence. Therefore, it always demands a separate forum. In this modern era, customers and parties face new problems. Therefore, the states are trying to find or enact new legal forums or systems to make the business environment smoother and more suitable for the parties, especially the consumers.

Consumers have some fundamental rights, and every State must protect those rights. However, the United Nations also have some guidelines to protect the rights of consumers.¹ There must be a body and forum to hear a consumer if any dispute arises between the two parties regarding their rights. In the guideline, the UN suggested that a fair, transparent, accessible, speedy, and effective dispute resolution system should be available in the

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¹ I Benöhr, 'The United Nations Guidelines for Consumer Protection: Legal Implications and New Frontiers' [2020] 43 Journal of Consumer Policy 105.

business. This system should not impose unnecessary costs or burdens upon the parties. The code or legislation enacting this system must be satisfactory to the parties and compatible with international law.² The UN also gave guidelines regarding e-commerce, financial services, and tourism. According to them, the signatory states must ensure a good business and physical safety environment.³

By resolution no 39/248 of 1985 UN sets some general principles to maintain a robust consumer protection environment and law. The governments should enact laws to protect consumers from hazards to their health and safety, promote their economic interest, educate consumers, restrict abusive business practices, ensure the flow of information, and to available hassle-free, adequate redress system. In this resolution, the state parties are suggested to standardise their business arena by following the guidelines.⁴ A body to regulate disputes to protect consumers' rights is mentioned and suggested in both the guideline and regulations. This body might be judicial or administrative.⁵

The research is based on a comparative method of study. The study focuses on a comparison of foreign laws and documents. The analysis related to the scenario in Bangladesh is based on the current law and expert commentaries collected for this study. Several pieces of literature from Pakistan, India, and Bangladesh have been considered as the basis of this study. Among them, Ahmed discussed the consumer protection laws of Pakistan and their application. According to him, Lahore Consumer Court is the largest consumer court in Pakistan. Consumers file complaints about defective services and products. However, they do not complain about false or misleading advertisements, non-issue of receipt an unfair trade practices.⁶

The current scenario of protecting the consumers' rights is analysed and described in the paper of Khan, Ali, Saleem, Naznin, and Shah. The authors believe that advertisement is the best way to showcase the product. Nevertheless, nowadays, consumers are wrongly informed by false advertisements. They mentioned the eight rights⁷ of consumers. The UN recognises these rights.⁸

Likewise, Pakistan and India enacted laws relating to consumer rights a long time ago. They updated their laws from time to time. As per the article of Verma, India removed its defects in mechanism, and how people are now getting remedies by the rules set up in the Consumer Protection Act 1986. It established consumer tribunals at the district and state

² UNCTAD, 'The United Nations Guidelines for Consumer Protection' (16 April 1985) Res 39/248, p 10

³ *ibid.* p 15

⁴ *ibid.*

⁵ *ibid.* para 28

⁶ Naveed Ahmed, 'Consumer Protection Laws and Application: A Case Study of Pakistan' [2020] 57 Journal of Research Society of Pakistan

⁷ The right to Safety, choice, be informed, remedy, be heard, service, environmental health and education.

⁸ Abdus Samad Khan *et al.*, 'Understanding and Analysis of Consumer Protection Laws in Pakistan' [2014] 4(12) Journal of Applied Environmental and Biological Sciences 92

levels to better protect consumer rights through a speedy and inexpensive adjudicative mechanism. Five hundred sixty-nine district forums ensured the implementation of the statutory provisions. The Department of consumer affairs was established in 1991 for the consumer movement. The author gave light on the changes to Consumer Protection Act 1993. This amendment reformed the consumer court. The government also set up consumer grievance cells in the industries and involved more media interest in consumer issues.⁹

In his article, Hossain detects the loopholes between the legislation, judicial power, and legal forum for the sufferings of the consumers of Bangladesh. According to the author, Bangladesh should follow the judicial framework of the neighbouring country India. He also summarises the present condition of the laws protecting consumers' rights. In his paper, he briefly described laws that indirectly protect consumer rights. He suggested increasing the number of fines and punishments.¹⁰ Again, in another article, Hossain tried to establish a comparative study of the legal mechanism of Bangladesh and India. Here the author mentioned the consumer court of India.¹¹

Previous studies emphasised different legal systems and laws to protect consumer rights. According to those studies, the laws and legal procedures regarding consumer protection in Bangladesh are not well-established as a developing county. In contrast, with time, Pakistan and India develop their laws and enforcing authorities. The authors also criticised the existing legislation and suggested adding new provisions and reconstructing the system to protect the consumers' rights, unlike in neighbouring countries. So, there is a gap of study in the corporate legal forums of Bangladesh.

Therefore, the current study will scrutinise the existing legal forum and find loopholes. The study also discusses the legal forum of Pakistan and India's legal forums to understand the difference between them and Bangladesh and the lacking of Bangladesh's forum or consumer rights protection process.

This study emphasises only the legal forum to protect the consumers' rights. The whole legal system of consumer dealings is no concern in this study. This study, however, selected the legal forum of India and Pakistan to discuss for understanding the legal forum of Bangladesh and tries to explore a new path for Bangladesh. These three countries belong to the same continent, and it is the limitation of this research not to discuss other regions. Most foreign data are collected using web sources, and the mentionable limitation is not to visit the practice of those countries in person.

⁹ DPS Verma, 'Developments in Consumer Protection in India' [2002] 25 Journal of Consumer Policy 117

¹⁰ Md. Emran Hossain, 'A Focus on the Legal Framework of Consumer Protection: Bangladesh Perspective' [2019] 5 Ideas 134

¹¹ Md. Emran Hossain, 'Consumer Protection of Bangladesh in the Experience of India: A Proposed Legal Framework' [2020] 9(1) Vivekananda Journal of Research 39

The legal forum of Bangladesh is still weak in protecting the rights of consumers. Quick remedy, judicial action is needed to protect their right. Forums introduced in Bangladesh are inactive. Therefore, maybe this is high time to rethink this issue and establish a new effective legal forum for reconstructing the previous legal systems.

Consumer Legal Forum of Pakistan

In Pakistan, there are different Consumer Protection laws for different provinces. There is no consolidated law for the whole nation. The laws are enacted according to the socioeconomic condition of each province. Some of them are Islamabad Consumer Protection Act- 1995, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Consumer Protection Act 1997, Balochistan Consumer Protection Act 2003, Punjab Consumer Protection Act 2005, and Sindh Consumer Protection Act 2014.

Legal Forum of Islamabad Consumers Protection Act 1995

Islamabad Consumers Protection Act was enacted in 1995 only for the territory of the capital Islamabad.¹² As per the Act of 1995, a council will be formed to promote and protect the right to information about quality, quantity standard, and price of goods and services and recommend laws and regulations regarding consumer protection.¹³ The Federal Government will appoint the chairman of this council.¹⁴

The Court of Sessions of Islamabad will entertain consumer protection cases according to their jurisdiction.¹⁵ After considering the complaint and reply, the authority can call evidence or the party to hear or conduct an inquiry or order for investigation.¹⁶

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Consumer Protection Act 1997

In 1997, Consumer Protection Act was enacted for the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. In 2015, this Act of 1997 was amended last time by Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Consumer Protection (Amendment) Act 2015

The government is bound to establish Consumer Court in every district of this province. Consumer Court established under this Act will be presided over by the district and Session Judge of that district.¹⁷ Any aggrieved consumer, associate, or director can file a complaint. In this case, the limitation period is ten days.¹⁸ Besides the Court, the Director of Industries and Commerce, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, the director¹⁹ under this Act, can also hear the dispute.

¹² Islamabad Consumers Protection Act 1995, s 1(2)

¹³ *ibid*, s 5

¹⁴ *ibid*, s 3

¹⁵ *ibid*, s 6

¹⁶ *Ibid*, s 8

¹⁷ Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Consumer Protection Act 1997, s 11(a)

¹⁸ *ibid*, s 13

¹⁹ *ibid*, s 2(ff)

The Balochistan Consumers Protection Act 2003

Balochistan Consumers Protection Act was enacted in 2003. Under this statute, there will be a Consumer Court in every district of Balochistan Province. The government will appoint judges of this Court or confer the power of this Court to any of the Judicial Magistrates by consulting the High Court Division.²⁰ The aggrieved or the council can file the complaint within ten days of the rise of the cause of action.²¹ The consumer court will follow the procedure of the Code Civil Procedure 1908 to serve the processes or Commission.²²

The Punjab Consumer Protection Act 2005

In Punjab, the consumer protection act is called The Punjab Consumer Protection Act 2005. Corporate legal forums are mentioned in parts VI, VII, and VIII. As per the provision of this statute, there will be a consumer protection council to protect and promote the rights of consumers.²³

The district coordinating officer will hear the disputes regarding consumer protection. He has the right to order police to collect evidence on the matter. For every district of the province of Punjab, there will be one or more separate consumer courts presided over by the District Judge or Additional District Judge. After receiving the complaint, the Court can order a settlement in the pre-stage trial. If the claim is minor or legally incapacitates any person, the Court will try to settle the dispute mutually.²⁴ The Court will decide the claim within six months from the receiving date of notice by the defendant.²⁵ The Lahore High Court Division will hear the appeal from the decision of The Consumer Courts.²⁶

The Sindh Consumer Protection Act 2014

The Sindh Consumer Protection Act was enacted in 2014. A consumer protection council will be formed under the Law of 2014.²⁷ The consumer legal forum under this statute is similar to the Punjab Consumer Protection Act 2005.

For judicial remedy, the government will establish Consumer Court in each district of Sindh province. Any Judicial Magistrate will preside over the Court. Sindh High Court will hear the appeal against the decision of the Consumer Court. In this case, the limitation period is 30 days.²⁸

²⁰ The Balochistan Consumers Protection Act 2003, s 12

²¹ *ibid*, s 14

²² *ibid*, s 15

²³ The Punjab Consumer Protection Act 2005, s 24

²⁴ *ibid*, s 25

²⁵ *ibid*, s 30(5)

²⁶ *ibid*, s 33

²⁷ The Sindh Consumer Protection Act 2014, s 25

²⁸ *ibid*, s 34

Though Pakistan has no unified law to protect consumer rights, like India, there are separate laws and forums for consumer right. There is a Consumer Protection Council in both countries. The procedure to try any dispute is the same for every province's administrative and legal forums. Most importantly, the laws of these countries are updated from time to time. It indicates that as a state, Pakistan and India are well concerned about the right of their consumer and fair trade.

Legal Forums of India

India is a big country with a massive amount of population. A massive amount of population means a large number of consumers. India has taken statutory measures for consumer protection to protect these consumers' rights a long time ago. In 1966 the first step was to protect consumer rights by establishing the Consumer Guidance Society (CGS). However, the consumers did not enjoy the statutory provisions without unified and effective mechanisms. Therefore, Monopolistic and Restrictive Trade Practices (MRTP) were introduced in 1969. It unified the scattered provisions relating to consumer protection under different laws.

The Consumer Protection Act was enacted in 1986 with more protection and a new mechanism. It protects by establishing special forums at the district, State, and national levels. These tribunals are empowered to give specific relief, compensation, and whatever is necessary. A Central Consumer Protection Council is established under this statute. The minister of the consumer affairs ministry will be the chairman of this council.²⁹ In every State, a state Consumer Protection Council, consisting of ten members,³⁰ will be established. In every district, there is a district council presided by the collector.³¹ These councils hear the consumer's problems³² and promote and assure consumers' interests and rights.

There are Consumer Dispute Redress Agencies at the state and National levels to hear and give remedies to the aggrieved consumers. There are Districts forums in every district for the same reason.³³ In the State, it is called the 'State Commission,' and at the national level, it is known as the 'National Commission.' The pecuniary jurisdiction of the state Commission is above 2 lac rupees.³⁴ The National Commission has administrative control of the state commission, and the state commission has administrative control over the district forum.³⁵ In case of penalties, the district forum, State, and national Commission

²⁹ The Consumer Protection Act 1986, s 4

³⁰ *ibid*, s 7

³¹ *ibid*, 8(A)

³² *ibid*, s 5

³³ *ibid*, s 9

³⁴ *ibid*, s 17

³⁵ *ibid*, s 24(A)

hold the power of Magistrate of the first class. The offences under this Act are being tried summarily.³⁶

The procedure of legal forums became more specific and more robust in India with a landmark decision in 1989. In this case, Monopolies and Restrictive Trade Practices (MRTP) ruled that based on any complaint of an aggrieved, the authority will conduct the investigation, examine or cross-examine the parties. They will have the power to call for documents or any other evidence.³⁷ In 1991 a separate Department of Consumer Affairs was set up as a part of the Central Ministry. It was later named the Ministry of Consumer Affairs, Food, and Public Distribution.

In 1993 the Consumer Protection Act 1986 was amended. This amendment formed a selection committee to appoint the chairman and member of the consumer tribunal. It also empowered the forums with additional power to order various kinds of remedies for the aggrieved.³⁸

Now online marketing is in trend. People buy and sell products online by using the online transaction method. So, rights are also infringed on online. So, there need to be new rules to face the problem. The Act of 1986 was replaced by The Consumer Protection Act 2019 in India. It came into force in July 2020. This Act added the offences or activities that hindered the consumer's rights through the digital medium.³⁹ In this new law, e-commerce and electronic provider is defined.⁴⁰ It includes unfair, unlawful, and unethical activities through electronic records as unfair trade practices.⁴¹

The Act of 2019 establishes State and District councils.⁴² As per this statute, there will be an investigating wing to investigate the complaints.⁴³ This investigating authority has the power to enter and search reasonable and necessary premises. They can seize any document, evidence, goods, or product.⁴⁴

Similar to the Act of 1986,⁴⁵ the Act of 2019 also provides a rule to establish District⁴⁶, State⁴⁷, and National⁴⁸ The Supreme Court held that the forum would decide the

³⁶ *ibid*, s 27

³⁷ *Voluntary Organisation in the Interest of Consumers Education (VOICE) v Delhi Bottling Co. (P.) Ltd.*, Monopolies and Restrictive Trade Practices Commission, 16 Jan 1989

³⁸ Verma (n 9)

³⁹ 'Consumer Protection Act 2019

⁴⁰ The Consumer Protection Act 2019, s 2(16)(17)

⁴¹ *ibid*, s 2(47)

⁴² *ibid*, s 6,8

⁴³ *ibid*, s 15

⁴⁴ *ibid*, s 22

⁴⁵ The Consumer Protection Act 1986

⁴⁶ The Consumer Protection Act 2019, s 28

⁴⁷ *ibid*, s 42

⁴⁸ *ibid*, s 53

jurisdiction first.⁴⁹ The district commission can order the parties and their lawyers to sit for mediation if the president of the Commission finds the element of mediation.⁵⁰

India has introduced Alternative Dispute Resolutions to settle the dispute regarding consumer rights. Under Chapter V of this Act of 2019, the government will create a mediation cell to settle the dispute outside the Court.⁵¹ District, State, or national Commissions can nominate the mediators.⁵²

Legal Forum of Bangladesh under The Consumers' Rights Protection Act-2009

Before enacting the Consumer Protection Act of 2009, there was no dedicated law to protect consumers' rights. That means there was no forum. Nevertheless, after enacting the Law of 2009, some courts are empowered with the responsibility to protect consumers. By this statute, executive and judicial remedies become available for the aggrieved. To protect the rights of consumers, the Bangladesh government enacted the Consumers Protection Act in 2009. It came into force on the 14 April of the same year. Though there were sporadic consumer protection provisions, this statute gathered all the provisions in a tie for the first time. It is the only statute that works to protect consumers' rights.

It defines consumers.⁵³ It also mentioned 12 activities⁵⁴ as anti-consumer practices. These are the criminal offenses under this Act. This Act also provides punishments for these anti-consumer practices.⁵⁵ Most importantly, there are three ways to get a remedy for infringement of any customer's right under this legislation.

Administrative Forum:

Any aggrieved person can file a complaint to the Directorate of the National Consumer's Right Protection (DNCRP). The government will appoint a director general for this purpose.⁵⁶ The director general can order of investigation⁵⁷ and issue a warrant⁵⁸ if he thinks it fits. Any district magistrate will have the same power as the director general.⁵⁹

An assistant director of DNCRP, who is mentioned here as Subject 1, shared his view regarding the current situation of the authority and administrative forum established under CRPA 2009. He admitted that the rate of complaints for infringement of consumers' rights

⁴⁹ *K Sagar, MD, Kiran Chit Fund vs A Bal Reddy* [2008] SC of India, 11 June 2008

⁵⁰ The Consumer Protection Act 2019, s 37

⁵¹ The Consumer Protection Act 2019, s 74

⁵² *ibid*, s 76

⁵³ The Consumers' Right Protection Act 2009, s 2(19)

⁵⁴ *ibid*, s 2(20)

⁵⁵ The Consumers' Right Protection Act 2009, Ch IV

⁵⁶ The Consumers' Right Protection Act 2009, s 20

⁵⁷ *ibid*, s 23

⁵⁸ *ibid*, s 24

⁵⁹ *ibid*, s 69

under The Consumers Rights Protection Act 2009 has been rising rapidly, especially since COVID-19. However, there is a lack of human resources and technical support. So, sometimes they face problems in taking immediate action on any complaint. In that case, the consumer has to be patient for a while.

Criminal Forum

Punishments under Chapter IV are mainly criminal remedies that include fines and imprisonment. Chapter V mentioned the legal forum, which will try the complaints. All offenses under this Act are cognisable, compoundable, and bailable.⁶⁰ A magistrate of first class or any metropolitan magistrate will try these offenses that occurred under his local jurisdiction.⁶¹ This trial will be a summary trial⁶² under The Code of Criminal Procedure 1898.⁶³ Aggrieved from any decision of the magistrate court can appeal to the session judge court within 60 days.⁶⁴

The current works of the criminal forum mentioned in CRPA 2009 can be summarised from the interview of Subject 2, a Senior Magistrate. Subject 2 never received any complaints under this Act of 2009. He received cases under the Standard of Weight and Measure Act 1982. However, the rate of these complaints is so less in number.

Civil Forum

Any consumer can file a complaint to a civil court to get a remedy for breaching his right even if a criminal case is in process or a criminal trial convicts the party.⁶⁵ Only the joint district judge of the concerned locality will be considered a civil court in this case.⁶⁶ In case of assessable consideration for any damage by the seller, the buyer can file a suit for compensation up to five times the assessable money.⁶⁷ The judge can order to compensate or replace or take back the goods.⁶⁸ An aggrieved can appeal to the High Court Division within 90 days.⁶⁹

Now the question comes whether this forum is active or not. The answer can be found in the interview of Subject 3, a Joint District Judge Court. Subject 3 assured that he never received any complaint under the Consumer Protection Act 2009. In his opinion, the lengthy process of the civil Court is the main reason. Aggrieved consumers prefer quick

⁶⁰ *ibid*, s 59

⁶¹ *ibid*, s 57

⁶² The Penal Code 1860 s 2(19)

⁶³ The Consumers' Right Protection Act 2009, s 58

⁶⁴ *ibid*, s 65

⁶⁵ *ibid*, s 66(1)

⁶⁶ *ibid*, s 66(2)

⁶⁷ *ibid*, s 66(3)

⁶⁸ *ibid*, s 67

⁶⁹ *ibid*, s 68

remedies. Subject 2 suggested that a separate judicial or quasi-judicial body may effectively solve this problem.

From the above discussion, it is clear that the forums established under CRPA 2009 are not active that much. Maximum times victims go to administrative forums as they will get 25% of the finned money. However, under CRPA-2009, in all cases from all forums, the aggrieved consumer will get a 25% share of the fine.⁷⁰ However, the negative part is that no case can be filled directly to the Magistrate. At first, a consumer has to file a complaint to the Director general, or any other officer appointed or empowered to do the function.⁷¹

Moreover, this Act has provisions that will help the consumers to get a remedy after being aggrieved. The legal forum under this Act is confusing and may lead to an unlawful advantage for the consumer.

Findings

Consumer rights protection is a worldwide concern now. Protecting consumer rights is essential to attract more and more foreign investment. Nevertheless, after discussing laws relating to Consumers Protection, some loopholes are shed light on. These loopholes are mentioned below:

- a. There are almost 61 laws to control some crimes or civil wrongs.⁷² These crimes or wrongs were named anti-consumer practices in 2009 by enacting The Consumers Rights Protection Act. Nevertheless, this statute does not cover all the new forms of infringement. On the other hand, its legal forum is complicated and confusing. Whereas India has amalgamated all laws and enacted one unified law, Pakistan enacted different laws relating to consumer rights protection for every State to remove confusion.
- b. Though there are almost ten types of legal forums under these laws, including administrative and special tribunals and ordinary civil and criminal courts⁷³, there is no dedicated court for consumer protection under the Law of 2009. India now has 610 districts and 35 state forums that protect consumers' rights.⁷⁴ Likewise, in

⁷⁰ *ibid*, s 76

⁷¹ *ibid*, s 71

⁷² Md. Nayem Alimul Hyder, 'Consumer's Rights Protection in Bangladesh' *The Financial Express* (26 April 2017) <<https://thefinancialexpress.com.bd/views/consumers-rights-protection-in-bangladesh>> accessed 28 December 2021

⁷³ *ibid*.

⁷⁴ Shanon, 'How Many Consumer Courts Are There in India' (Nobroker, 9 November 2021) <<https://www.nobroker.in/forum/how-many-consumer-courts-are-there-in-india/>> accessed 25 September 2022

Pakistan, there are four consumer courts in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province, 17 in Punjab, and 28 in Sindh Province.⁷⁵

- c. Most importantly, Bangladesh still has no provision to fight back against the wrongs done in e-commerce, whereas the e-commerce or digital commerce sector is developing very fast. However, India has enacted new provisions regarding e-commerce and wrong done by using digital ways in their newly enacted law of 2019.
- d. Moreover, under the Act of 2019, any consumer cannot go to Court. He has to file the complaint to the director or consumer rights association. And then, if the director thinks it fits, he will file the complaint to the Court. On the other hand, the court process is time-consuming. Moreover, the time and cost needed in Court are not worth it in comparison to the compensation given by the judge. On the other hand, it is time-consuming and easy to file a case in Court as India and Pakistan established dedicated corporate legal forums to give remedies to the aggrieved consumers. The victims can go to the Court on their own. So, the success rate of these forums in India and Pakistan is increasing.

From the above point, it is clear that Bangladesh is staying behind India and Pakistan in the case of consumer rights protection. It should reconstruct the structure of consumer rights protection by following India and Pakistan's model.

Conclusion

Consumer rights are new in concept. The world is considering it challenging to show their concern about the consumers. To establish a welfare country protecting consumer rights is a must. Like other countries, Bangladesh is taking initiatives to protect consumer rights. It has enacted new laws and regulations relating to it. After all these efforts, there are some loopholes in Bangladesh's legislation.

No active unified law, confusion about the law and forum, illiteracy about consumer rights, and backdated existing laws can be considered the main reasons for the infringement of consumer rights. People are not aware of these rights and legal forums and remedies. The government and concerned authorities have to make awareness among the mass people.

The legal forums in Bangladesh are insufficient to protect consumers' rights. A Separate corporate legal forum is a must. Moreover, the existing laws should have provisions for e-commerce and ADR. The suggestions which have been mentioned above are not exhaustive. However, these suggestions can bring a positive change in the sector it has been given. There may be some other suggestions that can also be inserted through an amendment. Even then, the above points can ensure that all the aggrieved consumers will

⁷⁵ Consumer Rights Commission of Pakistan (CRCP), 'Consumer Court Addresses and Contacts' (CRCP) <<https://crpc.org.pk/consumer-court-addresses-and-contacts/>> accessed 26 September 2022

get the proper remedy, which will motivate the aggrieved consumers to ask for legal remedy instead of mere compensation.

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